

FRICITION AND WEAR PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOTUBE/ALUMINA COMPOSITES UNDER WATER LUBRICATED CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

An alumina composite reinforced with 10 vol.% acid-treated multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) is prepared by a simple mechanical mixing method followed by a spark plasma sintering. The effects of friction conditions such as contact pressure and sliding velocity on tribological properties of the composite in a water lubricated environment are investigated using a ball-on-disk technique against an alumina ball. In addition, the Stribeck curves, showing boundary, mixed and hydrodynamic lubrication, are presented for the composite and monolithic alumina. It has been demonstrated that the composite shows lower coefficient of friction (COF) ($\mu \sim 0.1$) compared with the MWCNT-free monolithic alumina ($\mu \sim 0.2$) in the mixed regime (the initial contact pressure and sliding velocity are 0.6 GPa and 0.10 m/s, respectively). This may be attributable to the formation of the water film which is expected to be formed by hydrogen bonds with the functional group introduced into MWCNTs by the acid treatment. The COFs of the composite and monolithic alumina decrease with the increasing Stribeck parameter, and the COF at the initial contact pressure of 0.4 GPa and sliding velocity of 0.16 m/s was approximately 0.01, suggesting that the lubrication regime may be in hydrodynamic lubrication. The specific wear rates of the counterparts are typically in the range of 1.9×10^{-8} – 2.8×10^{-8} mm³/Nm, and these values are decreased with the increasing Stribeck parameter. These results suggest that the COF and specific wear rate vary with the operating conditions under water lubrication, which reflects the transition of the lubrication mode of the composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Since carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are considered to have lubrication properties [1] as well as high tensile strength and elastic modulus [2], incorporating CNTs into a ceramic matrix might be expected to improve both tribological and mechanical properties. The tribological properties of the materials are reportedly influenced by operating conditions and material characteristics [3,4]. Thus the understanding of those effects on the tribological properties is the prerequisite for the reliability evaluation and making decisions on fundamental material design of the composites. Lim et al. [5] investigated the tribological properties of hot-pressed MWCNT/alumina composites against a silicon nitride ball by using a ball-on-reciprocating type tribometer under ambient conditions. The authors reported that when the MWCNT content increased from 0 to 12 mass%, the coefficient of friction (COF) gradually decreased from 0.5 to 0.3. The wear loss of the composites decreased with increasing multi-walled CNT (MWCNT) content up to 4 mass%, but increased with further addition of MWCNT. Kim et al. [6] used a zirconia ball as a counterpart to investigate the friction and wear properties of the MWCNT/alumina composites. The COF, measured by using a ball-on-disk type tribometer under ambient conditions, immediately decreased by addition of a small amount of MWCNT, and measured

COF of the composite with 3 vol.% MWCNT was 0.16. The wear rate decreased with increasing MWCNT content and then leveled off when the MWCNT content exceeds 1.5 vol.%. The literatures reported previously show that the addition of MWCNT into ceramics seems to give favorable friction and wear properties under the air condition [5-10], while no groups have evaluated the tribological properties of CNT-reinforced ceramic composites under water lubrication. Therefore, in-depth understanding for tribological performance of CNT/ceramic composites under water lubrication conditions requires further research. In this study, MWCNT/alumina composites were prepared, and tribological properties of the composites in distilled water were investigated and compared with those of the MWCNT-free alumina. Stribeck curves were used to illustrate lubrication mechanism of the composite under water lubrication.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The MWCNT material (supplied from Hodogaya Chemical, Japan) was synthesized by a catalytic chemical vapor deposition method followed by high-temperature annealing. The thermal treatment of the MWCNTs was carried out at a temperature of 2600°C under argon atmosphere, and the purity was claimed to be 99.5 % by the producer. The pristine MWCNTs were refluxed in 3:1 (volume ratio) concentrated sulfuric acid:nitric acid mixture at 60°C for 2 hours. Then, they were washed thoroughly with deionized water to be acid free, and finally dried in an oven at 60°C.

A mixture of 10.0 vol.% MWCNTs and alumina powder was prepared by a simple mechanical mixing method [11, 12]. The details of composite preparation can be found in the Ref. [11]. In brief, a certain amount of the acid-treated MWCNTs were dispersed in 20 cm³ isopropyl alcohol with the aid of ultrasonic agitation for 1.5 hours. An α -alumina (TM-DAR, TAIMEI CHEMICALS, Japan) was added to the slurry at the ratio of the 10.0 vol% MWCNTs to prepare approximately 5 g of MWCNT–alumina mixture and then mixed using a planetary mixer with two rotation axes (ARE-250, THINKY, Japan) at 2000 rpm for 2 h. The mixture was then dried in an air oven. The composite was prepared by spark plasma sintering (SPS, SPS-1050, Sumitomo Coal Mining, Japan) in vacuum. A graphite die and punchers with 20-mm diameter were used to form the sample. The sintering process was carried out under the conditions: 1300°C, 10 min, and 50 MPa. In order to compare the friction properties of the composite, a MWCNT-free monolithic alumina was prepared under the same processing conditions.

Friction tests were performed using a ball-on-disk tribometer (STRB1500L, Toei Scientific Industrial, Japan) under water lubricated conditions. An alumina ball of 5 mm in diameter was used against flat MWCNT/alumina or monolithic alumina sample surfaces. The water temperature was maintained to $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The contact pressure and sliding velocity were over the range 0.4–1.4 GPa and 0.05–0.16 m/s, respectively, and Stribeck parameters $S_0 = \eta v / pR$ (η is lubricant viscosity, v is sliding velocity, p is mean contact pressure and R is ball wear scar diameter) were calculated assuming the lubricant viscosity as constant during the friction tests ($\eta = 0.679\text{--}0.719$ mPa·s). The COF (μ) was calculated by taking into account the normal load applied and the friction force measured using a load cell. For the comparison, the friction properties of the composite and monolithic alumina samples were evaluated under the air conditions. The temperature was maintained to $29 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and the relative humidity to 40 % for the air condition. The specific wear rate (W_s) was defined as $W_s = V/PL$ (V is the mass loss, P is the normal load and L is sliding distance). Prior to the tests, all samples were ultrasonically cleaned in acetone and dried in the air oven at 60°C. The surface roughness was measured on a 3D laser scanning microscope (VK-X100 KEYENCE, Japan). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL JSM-6610, Japan) was used to investigate the microstructures. The test numbers and experimental conditions are summarized in Table 1.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The alumina powder with 10.0 vol.% acid-treated MWCNTs can be solidified by SPS to near-theoretical density (> 98%). Measured bending strength, fracture toughness and Vickers hardness are 471.1 ± 20.8 MPa, 4.03 ± 0.01 MPa·m^{1/2} and 14.2 ± 1.3 GPa, respectively. Fig. 1 shows the polished surface of the composite and monolithic alumina, respectively. The initial surface roughness (R_a) of the monolithic alumina and composite was 0.01 and 0.05 μm , respectively, and the R_a of the alumina ball was 0.05 μm . The higher R_a observed in the composite disk sample may be mainly attributed to

Test number	MWCNT volume fraction (vol.%)	Initial contact pressure, p_0 (GPa)	Sliding velocity, v (m/s)	Stribeck parameter, S_0 (-)	Sliding distance (m)
C-1	10.0	0.4	0.16	8.5×10^{-8}	36000
C-2		0.6	0.10	3.3×10^{-8}	
C-3		1.0	0.10	0.7×10^{-8}	
C-4		1.0	0.05	0.4×10^{-8}	
C-5		1.4	0.05	0.1×10^{-8}	
C-air	0.6	0.10	-		
A-1	0	0.4	0.16	7.2×10^{-8}	
A-2		0.6	0.10	2.7×10^{-8}	
A-3		1.4	0.05	0.1×10^{-8}	
A-air		0.6	0.10	-	

Table 1: Test number and experimental conditions.

Figure 1: Optical microscope images of polished surface of (a) composite and (b) monolithic alumina.

the existence of the MWCNTs in the grain boundary of the alumina matrix.

The results of the ball-on-disk tribometry studies under air condition carried out on the composite and monolithic alumina are shown in Fig. 2. The initial transition from low to high COF during the run-in regime is visible, and there is no clear difference in COF between two samples. The steady-state COF calculated by averaging the values for the last 50% of the sliding distance were 0.56 and 0.52 for the composite and monolithic alumina, respectively. The variations of COF are shown in Fig. 3 with respect to the sliding distance of the composite and monolithic alumina under water lubricated condition. Even though a region of high COF values can be visible at the beginning of the tests, the COFs tend to decrease with the increase of sliding distance. It is also seen that both COFs of the composite and monolithic alumina increase with increasing contact pressure and decreasing sliding velocity. The relatively high COF for the composite at the contact pressure of 1.4 GPa and sliding velocity of 0.05 m/s can be seen during the run-in regime where severe wear may occurred (friction surface of the disk and ball specimens are describe below in Figs. 4(h) and 5(h)).

Post-test microscopic analyses of the friction surfaces provided information that helped to elucidate the friction mechanisms. The friction surfaces on the monolithic alumina and composites, and corresponding counterparts tested are shown in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively. As shown in Fig. 4(a)-(b) and 4(d)-(f), no clear difference in the friction surfaces was observed under the friction conditions of initial contact pressure ($p_0 \leq 1.0$ GPa) and $v \geq 0.1$ m/s (test number: C-1–C-3, A-1 and A-2). The friction surfaces were generally smooth and only a little wear debris were accumulated at the edge of the

Figure 2: Variation of COF of composite and monolithic alumina under air condition with sliding distance.

Figure 3: Variation of COF of (a) composite and (b) monolithic alumina under water lubricated condition with sliding distance.

friction tracks. The surface profiles of the samples are also shown in Fig. 4. The composites, which were ultrasonically cleaned in acetone and dried in an air oven at 60°C , showed that no clear worn part at the contact regions were observed under the friction conditions of $p_0 \leq 1.0$ GPa and $v \geq 0.10$ m/s, suggesting that the composite suffered negligible wear. On the other hand, the wear volume can be calculated in the sample C-4, C-5 and A-3 (the friction conditions of $p_0 \geq 1.0$ GPa and $v = 0.05$ m/s), and their specific wear rates are in the range 0.9×10^{-8} – 2.1×10^{-8} $\text{mm}^3/\text{N}\cdot\text{m}$. For the counterparts (Fig. 5), the friction surfaces became flat where the counterparts were slid against the composites, demonstrating a wear during the friction tests. The specific wear rates of the counterparts were typically in the range of 0.7×10^{-8} – 5.6×10^{-8} mm^3/Nm , and they increased with the increasing contact pressure and decreasing sliding velocity. Figs. 4(h) and 5(h) show that for the friction condition of $p_0 = 1.4$ GPa and $v = 0.05$ m/s (test number: C-5), the wear surface is scratched (indicated by arrows), suggesting that an abrasive sliding wear mechanism. This is mainly due to the presence of wear debris on the friction surface.

Fig. 6 shows the COF plotted against the Stribeck parameter S_0 . In this figure, the COFs of the composite and monolithic alumina under air sliding condition are also indicated by arrows, and they are about twice as large as those under water lubricated condition. The two regimes of lubrication (boundary and mixed regime) can be distinguished. For monolithic alumina, the boundary regime is observed for $S_0 < 3 \times 10^{-8}$, where the COF is almost constant at a value of $\mu \sim 0.2$. In this regime, the

Figure 4: Friction surfaces on (a-c) monolithic alumina and (d-h) composites.

lubricant is almost fully absent from the contact zone, such that the surfaces are in direct contact. Note that the COF of the composite at the contact pressure of 1.4 GPa and sliding velocity of 0.05 m/s ($S_0 = 1 \times 10^{-9}$) was higher than that of monolithic alumina. This behavior may be due to the presence of the wear debris as mentioned above. The mixed regime is observed in the range of $3 \times 10^{-8} < S_0 < 7 \times 10^{-8}$ for the monolithic alumina and $7 \times 10^{-9} < S_0 < 8 \times 10^{-8}$ for the composite. In this regime more fluid is entrained in the contact as S_0 increases, resulting in less asperity contacts and hence a reduction in friction. It is also shown that the composite shows lower COF ($\mu \sim 0.1$) compared with the monolithic alumina ($\mu \sim 0.2$) when the S_0 is about 3.0×10^{-8} , suggesting that this COF reduction of ~ 0.1 can be attributed to the presence of the MWCNTs. The COFs of both samples at the initial contact pressure of 0.4 GPa and sliding velocity of 0.16 m/s ($S_0 = 7-8 \times 10^{-8}$) are approximately 0.01, which suggests that the lubrication regimes may be in hydrodynamic lubrication at $S_0 > 8 \times 10^{-8}$. These results revealed that the addition of MWCNTs is effective for decreasing COF under the boundary and mixed regime.

The parameters that influence the friction and wear properties may include MWCNTs' dispersibility and surface charge, in addition to the experimental conditions (lubricant viscosity, sliding velocity and contact pressure). In this study, we used the MWCNTs with high crystallinity, and they were acid-treated by the mixture of sulfuric acid and nitric acid. It has been shown that the acid treatment employed in this study resulted in the formation of surface carboxylic acid and other groups on the tube surfaces [13]. These kinds of functional groups on MWCNTs dissociate in ethanol and consequently impart negative charge on the MWCNTs. Thus, it can be expected that the larger electrical repulsive forces between nanotubes will facilitate their dispersion and prevent them from

Figure 5: Friction surfaces of alumina ball slid against (a-c) monolithic alumina and (d-h) composite.

Figure 6: Stribeck curves for composite and monolithic alumina.

tangling and agglomeration, which leads to the improvement of MWCNTs' dispersibility. Furthermore, the water film is expected to be formed by hydrogen bonds with the functional group introduced into MWCNT by an acid treatment, which can protect against alumina-alumina contact and leads to the decrease of the COF [14]. In view of the significance of MWCNT type and content, further studies should be carried out to examine the effects of the above-mentioned parameters in order to further improve the friction and wear properties of MWCNT/ceramic composites.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the alumina composite reinforced with 10 vol.% acid-treated MWCNTs is prepared, and the effects of friction conditions such as contact pressure and sliding velocity on friction and wear properties of the composite and monolithic alumina are investigated under water lubricated conditions using a ball-on-disk technique against an alumina ball. In addition, the Stribeck curves are presented for the composite and monolithic alumina. It was demonstrated that the COF and specific wear rate varied with the operating friction conditions under water lubrication. In the boundary lubrication regime (initial contact pressure, sliding velocity and Stribeck parameter (S_0) were 0.6 GPa, 0.10 m/s and 3×10^{-8} , respectively), the composite shows lower COF ($\mu \sim 0.1$) compared with the monolithic alumina ($\mu \sim 0.2$). This COF reduction of ~ 0.1 may be attributed to the presence of the acid-treated MWCNTs, and the water film on the friction surface is expected to be formed by hydrogen bonds with the functional group introduced into MWCNTs by an acid treatment. Furthermore, the COFs of both the composite and monolithic alumina decreased with the increasing Stribeck parameter. The COFs at the contact pressure of 0.4 GPa and sliding velocity of 0.16 m/s ($S_0 = 8 \times 10^{-8}$) was approximately 0.01, suggesting that the lubrication regimes may be in hydrodynamic lubrication. The specific wear rates of the counterparts were typically in the range of 0.7×10^{-8} – 5.6×10^{-8} mm³/Nm, and these values increased with the increasing Stribeck parameter.

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